

CarE-Service

**Circular economy business models
for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through
advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services**

NEW APPROACHES FOR COLLABORATIVE PRODUCT-SERVICE DESIGN

(Deliverable 3.1)

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Join our "Stakeholders' Group" and
"Consumers' Committee"

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the work performed under WP3 “Customer-driven products re-design for circular economy” and report outcomes of Task 3.1 “New approaches for collaborative product-service design”. It consists of a combined method of how to design product and services within value chains of Electric and Hybrid Electric Vehicles (E&HEV) with the focus on having parts and components repaired, reused, remanufactured and/or material recycled. The aim of this design method is to guide companies on how to design products in such a manner that repair, reuse, remanufacturing and recycling can be performed effective and efficiently.

This deliverable focuses on new collaborative approaches for designing products and services for circular economy. This proposed product-service design method are mainly consist of two parts. The first part is an Actors and System mapping which is followed by a Design-for-Re-use-Processes framework. These methods are defined to include in the design phase both industrial stakeholders in charge of performing re-use processes and final customers, whose product and service use experience depends on the re-designed products. This means that well-working information feedback is established to be able to react fast on possible problems during reuse and remanufacturing. Feedback is made possible through Design-for-Re-use-Processes framework that provide structural manner to deal with information flow in both directions in the supply chains. The result of this task will be the formalization of the new design methods including ways-of-working, together with an analysis of the organizational and technological requirements for the various organizations involved in the design to adopt such methods on a stable and continuous basis.

List of Acronyms

CC:	Consumers Committee
DfD:	Design-for-Disassembly
DfE:	Design-for-the-Environment
DfRem:	Design-for-Re-manufacturing
DfRP:	Design-for-Re-use-Processes
DfS:	Design-for-Sustainability
DfX:	Design-for-X
E&HEV:	Electric and Hybrid Electric Vehicles
EoL:	End-of-Life
EoU:	End-of-Use
GA:	Grant Agreement
ICT:	Information and Communication Technology
IPR:	Intellectual Property Rights
LPD:	Lean Product Development
PSS:	Product-Service Systems
SG:	Stakeholder Group
TPS:	Toyota Production Systems

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the **CarE-Service project** there are products, services and systems developed for the future Electric and Hybrid Electric Vehicles (E&HEV). These kinds of combinations of products, services and systems sometimes called Product-Service Systems (PSS) have been integrated and optimized from a life-cycle perspective in relation to customer values (modified from Meier et al (2010)). Developing a design method for PSS is usually more complex than only focusing on developing physical products. In order to develop PSSs for E&HEV a collaborative product-design method is useful to support the companies involved. Services are intangible and therefore more complex when it comes to measuring the quality of the final outcome (Desai et al (2017)) and thus put demands on the service that is going to be delivered (Åhlström, 2004).

In order to develop a well-functioning PSS the requirements from internal and external actors needs to be well understood as well as the necessary information exchange needed between them. Effective information flows are key to realizing effective PSS. According to Kurilova-Palisaitiene et al (2015) value chains that include remanufacturing commonly contain both information bottlenecks and lack of information at many actors along the value chains, see Figure 1. Within the **CarE-Service project** three value chains are being studied.

Figure 1: Common information losses and bottlenecks within value chain actors at each product life-cycle stage in the value chain (adapted from Kurilova-Palisaitiene et al, 2015).

These kind of information losses is something that the stakeholders of the **CarE-Service project** need to avoid by effectively sharing information to the right actors e.g. through the development of the ICT platforms in WP-6 within the **CarE-Service project**. In order to facilitate an efficient information flow among the value chains within the **CarE-Service project** as well as a collaborate product-service design, an Actors and System map needs to be drawn. According to Lindahl et al (2014) the Actors and System mapping method can be used for describing actors and activities between a provider and a customer within a PSS and thus suitable method to be used within this work package of the **CarE-Service project**.

Within this research project we are adopting a life cycle perspective, often referred to as a cradle-to-cradle perspective. This perspective considers the life cycle of a product to consist of several phases including raw material extraction, materials processing, manufacturing, assembly, distribution, use and end-of-life treatment. According to (e.g. Sundin, 2018) there are three main phases are *Beginning-of-Life* (BoL, including material acquisition, design and manufacture of parts, and assembly of products), *Middle-of-Life* (MoL, including product delivery, installation, and use, as well as maintenance, repair, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and reuse) and *End-of-Life* (EoL, including material recycling, upcycling, energy recovery, and landfilling) as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The product life cycle, including the three main phases: *Beginning-of-Life (BoL)*, *Middle-of-Life (MoL)*, and *End-of-Life (EoL)* adapted from Sundin (2018).

2 COLLABORATIVE PRODUCT-SERVICE DESIGN METHODS

This proposed product-service design method is based on a combination of two previously developed methods called “Actors and System Maps – A Methodology for Developing Product/Service Systems” by Desai et al (2017) and “Design-for-Re-use-Processes framework” by Lindkvist and Sundin (2016). Both these methods are developed over several years in close collaboration with manufacturing companies. Within the *CarE-Service project* these methods are combined and customized according to the requirements and needs of the value chains in the project. The following subchapters, 2.1 and 2.2, describe these customized design methods to be used in the *CarE-Service project*.

2.1 Actors and System Mapping

Within this subchapter the actors and system mapping method is described with its background and six steps of execution.

2.1.1 Background to Actors and System Mapping

The actors and system mapping aim to, on a relevant level of detail, visualize the network of actors involved in an existing or potential PSS or similar type of offering, and show the flow of products, services and information between them, as well as how the activities through these are managed. According to Desai et al (2017) these visualizations are useful, for example, when identifying important flows of information, services, products and activities. The visualizations can also be used for instance to identify the lack of information flows and activities or to show that existing ones not are necessary or optimal. This kind of knowledge is useful when developing a PSS or improving an already existing one, and this knowledge is often missing or is at a non-sufficient level of detail, especially concerning the overall understanding of the actors involved and the information flows and activities. This type of knowledge can also be transformed into PSS requirements that can be used for designing a PSS or when evaluating different PSS concepts. Desai et al (2017). The actors and system mapping consist of six steps (as depicted in Figure 3):

Figure 3: The six steps to follow within the Actors and System mapping method (Desai et al 2017).

According to Desai et al (2017) it is preferable to assign a facilitator is assigned to manage the method activities such as collecting results (Actors and System Maps) and arranging workshops during the mapping steps.

2.1.2 Step 1: Define the Product-Service System to be analyzed

Defining the PSS to be analysed includes deciding the focus and level of ambition for the analysis. It also includes on how to conduct the analysis in more detail. Depending on focus and situation the data collection and analysis can be conducted differently (as further described in the steps below).

2.1.3 Step 2: Identify actors involved and flows of product, services and information between actors

Identifying the actors involved and their flows of products, services and information between them can be conducted through two steps.

Firstly, known actors within the value chain are asked about their view on how the PSS is provided. By doing so, many actors can be identified and described. Usually, there are many views among the actors on how a PSS is provided. The actors identified can be company departments, functions, staff from e.g. sales, manufacturing, design, service, remanufacturing as well as customers and end-users. When identifying the actors, it is preferable from an overview perspective to categorise the different types of actors and colour code them in the actors map with different colours (as also suggested by Lindahl et al (2014), Donaldson et al (2006) and Tan (2010)).

Secondly, the actors are asked to identify important interactions (both flows and directions) between the identified actors. This means that larger flows of product, service and information should be marked in the actor map in between the actors. Here, material flows could e.g. be raw/recycled material, parts, components, products and waste. Services could on the other hand be e.g. education, installation, maintenance, and product use support. Information flows could e.g. regard product life cycle data information sharing on when maintenance is needed. All kinds of flows could be one-way or two-way interactions that should be marked by arrows. The different actors and flows should have different colours in order to get a good overview of the actor map, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: A generic example of an Actors map with actors and flows in different colours (adapted from Lindahl et al 2014). (actor names are excluded due confidentiality reasons).

In order to make the actors map one can use two different approaches;

- a) Ask different actors separately to plot their view of how the PSS is provided with its material, service and information flows;
- b) Ask different actor to meet during a focus group or workshop and then together plot how the PSS is provided.

The a) approach is a bit more time-consuming than the b) approach but on the other hand the a) approach can give you a better insight on how each actor sees his or her view without any influences from other actors. The b) approach is faster and a common and coherent view of how the PSS is provided is achieved. For both approaches it is recommended to use a whiteboard or similar in order to sketch the flows and maybe erase flows as the actor representatives are discussing the map. When making the mapping it is sometimes needed to breakdown one actor into several actors depending on e.g. what information is shared with whom in a department. The level of details of the actor map needs often to be of a high to make it useful and not miss any important actors or flows.

2.1.4 Step 3: Analyze if identified actors and the flows of products, services, and information are at sufficient level of detail

To decide if the level of detail of the actor map is sufficient a workshop with the actors should be held. This is especially important if the mapping has been conducted separately with each actor in the identification step (Step 2). At the workshop it is decided among the participants if the level of detail is enough. At this stage there could be decision made that more actors should be included in the map and needs further investigations.

2.1.5 Step 4: Identify activities used to manage products, services and information

In this step a system map is created which visualise the activities that are utilized to achieve the interactions between the actors. These activities are characterized by the condition in which things are conducted including support systems, methods and processes. The activities are marked with boxes in the system map, see Figure 5. During the life of PSS there are different activities occurring which can be illustrated in the system map, see Figure 5. The identification of activities can as in the identification of actors be conducted with each actor separately or in a group with a focus on major and important activities.

Figure 5: Part of a generic example of a **System map** that illustrates actors involved in the ongoing execution of a PSS and what activities they perform. The darker lines are showing the flows during the execution stage (adapted from Desai et al (2017)). (actor names are excluded due confidentiality reasons).

2.1.6 Step 5: Analyze if identified activities are at a sufficient level of detail

In this step the level of detail is analysed by the actors in a workshop setting. Within this step it could be discovered that more activities should be added to the system map. This step is especially useful when the activities have been identified separately by different actors.

2.1.7 Step 6: Identify possible improvements

As a final step the actors and system map is analysed with the objective to find possible improvements. Depending on the purpose for making the actor and system map this step can be analysed deep or shallow. In some cases, the actor and system map is made to achieve a good overview of how the PSS is executed, and for that purpose only. Improvements discovered in this step could for example be getting better information flows, finding activities that could have more actors involved to reach better PSSs.

Within the **CarE-Service project** the actors and system map will be useful to understand which actors that needs to be involved in order to achieve collaboration between the actors with the aim of providing the customers high quality products and service in an efficient and effective

manner. The actors and system map will also be an useful input to the design method that follows in the next subchapter.

2.2 Design-for-Re-use-Processes framework

Having a life-cycle perspective (see Figure 2) on combined product and services mean that life-cycle considerations must be considered for both physical products used in the PSS and the services used during and between the contract times. The physical products can be adapted in various ways for the product life-cycle according to DfX methodologies. For this, there exist many engineering methods that would result in adaptation for manufacturing, delivery, usage, service, disassembly, reassembly, testing, recycling and/or remanufacturing. (Sundin, 2009) In Deliverable 1.2 of the **CarE-Service project** there are several guidelines of design for reuse, remanufacturing and recycling described. These kinds of DfX-methodologies have been used in industry for a long time and are continuously improved. For example, the FCA group within the **CarE-Service project** started with Design-for-Disassembly (DfD) in the early 1990s which was then evolved into Design-for-the-Environment since the late 1990s and starting from year 2000 the company group are more working with Design-for-Sustainability (DfS) including the balancing with customer costs, safety etc. Within this CarE-Service project and especially this third work package on design will assist FCA to advance their DfS program to consider the future re-use processes in their product and service development.

The Design-for-Re-use-Processes (DfRP) framework is directed to companies that can control PSS design and re-use processes, and specifically supports integration of information from re-use processes into the design process in order to better adapt products for re-use processes. With products designed for re-use processes, the long-term goal is to improve the effectiveness and efficiency in the re-use processes. For the **CarE-Service project** these processes are described in Deliverable 1.2 called “D1.2 Analysis and specifications of re-use value chains”. The DfRP framework is based on back casting principles and consists of four steps as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The framework supports implementation of feedback from re-use processes to product design in for steps and by continuous improvements (adapted from Lindkvist Haziri and Sundin (2019)).

Firstly, the current situation is assessed in Step 1 and thereafter the future vision is outlined in Step 2. Step 3 provides actions for stepwise implementation of feedback from re-use processes to design. These actions are prioritized and a time plan is created. The first action identified is then carried out. The final step is an evaluation of the effects of the implemented actions, and the effect that it has regarding Design-for-Re-use-processes. Further, Step 4 is a checkpoint to evaluate if the plan created in Step 3 needs revising or not. There after the method steps are repeated until the vision is fulfilled (Table 1).

2.2.1 Step 1: Assess current state

In this first step of the framework the already made actors and system map (subchapter 2.1) should be used as a base. Here, the current situation regarding the information feedback flows is assessed. The assessment is done via interviews with actors in the product design department and within the re-use processes; in this case, relevant staff within the product development department such as managers, design engineers, and project managers should be interviewed. Likewise, within the re-use process organization, managers and technicians should be interviewed. These individuals, representing one of the appointed actors (e.g. project manager), should preferably be interviewed separately in order to obtain answers reflecting reality rather than what is accepted internally as policy, etc.

Table 1: Contents of the Design-for-Re-use-Processes framework that supports implementation of feedback from re-use processes to product design (adapted from Lindkvist Haziri and Sundin (2019)).

Step	Input	Tools	Activities	Output	Actors
1. Assess current state	Information about actual information flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors and system map Interview guide Information flow chart 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews Illustrations Analyse Communicate results 	Coherent understanding of current information flows	Product design leaders Project leaders Re-use process mgmt
2. Outline future vision	Information about feedback implementation actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback implementation action list 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Back casting Set goals Choose actions Prioritize Choose products or components Make time plan 	Action plan	Mgmt Design Re-use process
3. Improve feedback strategies	Action plan and information flow illustration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Re-design checklists and tools Feedback implementation actions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initialize Utilize support Document process 	Changes in feedback transfer	Design Re-use process
4. Evaluate	Products and components design features Action plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Re-design checklists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document re-design checklists Evaluate future vision (Step 1) Evaluate time plan (Step 2) Evaluate and continue implementation (Step 3) 	Complete evaluation sheet Revised action plan	Design Re-use process Mgmt

The interview set up is based on getting input from design, manufacturing, service and re-use processes regarding the information transfer. A set of questions is described in Table 2. The outlook in many companies is that there is little or no information transfer from re-use processes to design, thus the questions cannot solely focus on that subject but rather aim at painting a picture of what the information transfer looks like regarding the design and re-design processes. It is important not only to see and visualise the information transfer process, but indeed to verify the conditions for the information transfer. Although systems for information sharing and transfer are in place the picture of what the information transfer looks like will probably vary a bit depending on who in the staff is asked. Every department will have knowledge about their information flows, but in this step the collective view is explored. It is important that the interviews are carried out by an unbiased person. The interviewees should feel compelled to answer freely to the questions so that the answers

reflect the real and not the ideal situation. It is also important that the aim of the interview is clearly defined and that the respondent has got the information well before the interview so that he or she can prepare by thinking over the questions. An interview guide including the aim and purpose of the interview as well as contact details of the interviewer should be prepared. Together with the guide, the interview questions (Table 2) should be made available so that the interviewee can prepare his or her answers properly in order to get the best results out of the interview.

Table 2: Interview questions to representatives from design (adapted from Lindkvist Haziri and Sundin (2019)).

Questions to the design department	
Subject	Questions
Information to design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What information does <i>design</i> receive from <i>re-use processes</i>? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. How is that information transferred (channel/system)? 1.2. How is that information used? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2.1. When in the design process is that information used? 1.3. What information is most important? 1.4. Is there information that is not used? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.4.1. If so, why is that information not used? 1.5. What other information could be useful for <i>design</i>?
Information from manufacturing and service	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. What other information does <i>design</i> receive from <i>manufacturing</i> and <i>service</i>? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1. How is that information transferred (channel/system) 2.2. How is that information used? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.2.1. When in the design process is that information used? 2.3. What information is most important? 2.4. Is there information that is not used? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.4.1. If so, why is that information not used? 2.5. What other information could be useful for <i>design</i>?
Information from other actors (here the Actors and System map is used)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. What other information does <i>design</i> receive from the other actors in the product life cycle (e.g. customers, suppliers, purchasers)? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1. How is that information transferred (channel/system)? 3.2. How is that information used? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.2.1. When in the design process is that information used? 3.3. What information is the most important? 3.4. Is there information that is not used? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3.4.1. If so, why is that information not used? 3.5. What other information could be useful for <i>design</i>?
Decisions and requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. How are the decisions taken in the <i>design</i> phase? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1 What criteria go into the design process? 4.2. What laws and regulations must be considered when designing the product? 4.3. What requirements does design have to include regarding EoU or EoL aspects (e.g. re-use, repair, remanufacturing and recycling)? 4.4 What are the entities of the requirements specification relevant to re-use processes?

During the interview, follow up questions and questions that will clarify the responses are required. This semi-structural approach will contain interview questions that will vary from interview to interview, and thus are not specified. A preferable approach for performing these interviews is to illustrate the information flows on e.g. a whiteboard while the interview is carried out. Thus, as an actor is brought up in the interview, the name of the that actor is also written down on the whiteboard. Likewise, as the information flows are described, lines will be drawn between the actors to illustrate the information exchange (similar to the Actors and System map described in subchapter 2.1).

The intention in this step is to capture the actual situation in a way that is illustrative of the reality. This might bring clarity to the current situation, and not only to the interviewer, but also to the interviewee. The illustration can then be used as a communication tool when merged together with the answers of the other relevant interviewees. Each profession will have their perspective of the complex system of how information is shared within the organisation. It is however very important that the interviewee gets an opportunity to verify his or hers answers. Hence, at the end of each interview the interviewer summarise the interview by reading the answers to the interview questions and let the interviewee verify, add to or correct the answers.

After all interviews have been conducted, the interviews need to be analysed. The analysis is carried out by drawing up information flows. More actors than the interviewed ones will be in the illustration. It could be valuable to interview them as well to get a richer picture, however the responses from the four actors **design**, **manufacturing**, **service** and **re-use processes** are enough to get at picture of the current situation. Indeed, the information feedback between **re-use processes** and **design** might be very different from how feedback is transferred from **manufacturing** and **design**. However, all information feedback found in the interviews should be included in the final illustration. Although the re-use processes may not provide feedback to design, the **re-use processes** need to be included as one of the actors in the final illustration. Thus, when setting up the illustration of the information flows, start by placing **design**, **manufacturing**, **service** and **re-use processes**. This illustration can be seen as an upgraded actors and system map.

If carried out correctly, the assessment of the current state should be disseminated throughout the organisation and areas for improvement clearly pointed out. Often the

situation is not clear until the illustration is done, and it is easier to compare and contrast re-use process involvement in the information feedback than if only staff from *re-use processes* and *design* were interviewed. Preferably, areas for improvement should be discussed, clarified and summarised in a document.

2.2.2 Step 2: Outline future vision

When the current situation is mapped, analysed and communicated, the next step is to identify a vision of a desirable scenario: in other words, what the ideal scenario looks like concerning how feedback from the *re-use processes* should reach *design* and be integrated in the design process. This scenario should be outlined in a team of representatives from *design*, *re-use processes* and *management*. What the desired future vision is will be company dependent, however it should specify a principle-based scenario for optimal information feedback from the *re-use processes* to *design*.

When the initial mapping of the current stage and a clear vision has been established, there will be a gap between the current state and the vision. That gap is addressed in this framework by feedback implementation actions presented below. The actions are presented in order of complexity, starting with the assumed least complex action to take:

- **Genchi gembutsu** (“go and see for yourself”), where the design engineers visit the re-use process companies to learn about the re-use processes and specific issues. (Genchi gembutsu is one of the famous lean strategies of Toyota Production Systems (TPS) that refers to the fact that any information about a process will be simplified and abstracted from its context when reported. This has often been one of the key reasons why solutions designed away from the process seem inappropriate (Manufacturing Terms, 2019)).
- **Feedback from technicians in the re-use process facility**, collected via a software application (e.g. the ICT platform also developed within the *CarE-service project*).
- **Workshops/integration events**, where re-use process staff and product designers meet to learn from each other and solve problems.
- **An ombudsman for re-use processes**, appointed to speak for the re-use processes in the product development projects.

- **A fully integrated product development process**, where the re-use processes are also represented as one of the actors and value providers in the value chain.

These examples of actions are suggested based on findings in empirical studies and in Lean Product Development (LPD) literature, e.g. Liker et al (2006). The idea is that once the current stage and vision are clarified, different strategies for integrating feedback into the product design process should be discussed. The actions should be chosen based on the level of appropriateness for the specific case company. It should be pointed out, however, that not all these actions need to be taken; the best combination is to be decided by each company based on their assessed current state and outlined future vision.

In order to reach the desired vision outlined in Step 2, the actions are prioritized and specified in a time plan that will also include evaluations after each implementation action. Thus, when promising actions have been chosen, they should be ranked according to how easy they are to implement, then prioritized. Initially, easily implementable actions should be adopted. It is better to start taking actions in the aimed direction than to do nothing and wait for major changes if the different actions are not heavily interdependent. The actions will then be implemented stepwise and evaluated after a certain time period according to the company needs.

2.2.3 Step 3: Improve feedback strategies

The planned actions are implemented in this step. The actors will participate in the actions and the goal is that design will not only receive feedback from the re-use processes, but also get knowledge about the re-use processes and use the information and knowledge in the design process. For instance, if **Genchi gembutsu** is applied, the design engineers will visit the re-use process companies to learn about the re-use processes and specific issues. During the visit they can ask questions and get information about the used products and components first hand. They can also get a demonstration of how certain parts are disassembled and see with their own eyes how design features affect the re-use processes.

In the process of working with implementing the actions, the achieved information and knowledge needs to be captured. Such documentation is, for instance, design support such as design checklists (see Deliverable 1.2), guidelines and know-how sheets. Other documentation methods such as A3 reports (where all information of the improvement work

is written down and illustrated) and other intra-organizational documents will support the process of upholding the actions and continuous improvements.

When the strategies have been implemented and at a certain time interval (e.g. a few months), an evaluation follows. The evaluation will take place before the next implementation phase begins, and so on until the goal is reached.

2.2.4 Step 4: Evaluate

The evaluation phase consists of two parts. The first evaluation and success criteria that will indicate whether or not the increase of information feedback from re-use processes to product design has led to product design that are facilitating the re-use processes e.g. remanufacturing. Here, Design-for-Re-use process checklists could be used to verify the actions that have taken place during the implementation phases in order to promote e.g. design for remanufacturing. In the bullet list below, examples of design criteria for design for remanufacturing are listed (as an example of a re-use process):

- Use of standardized parts
- Robust material selections
- Modular design
- Upgradability
- Assembly methods that allows for non-destructive disassembly and reassembly
- Minimal number of connectors
- Reusable connectors
- Easy access to short-lived parts (wear and tear)
- Shapes that does not prevent cleaning
- Shapes which are easily using for re-forming
- Materials that are easy to clean
- Corrosion resistant parts
- Timeless (classic) design

Hence, the provided checklist should be used to verify what components were modified and to meet the requirements from, in this case, remanufacturing. For instance, component thickness may have been increased to allow reprocessing of goods (e.g. metal grinding of engines), or a more durable material may have been used on a critical component to prolong its predicted lifetime (e.g. metal instead of plastic or increased thickness in some parts of the bonnet structure when a material change occurs (e.g. from steel to lightweight materials such as aluminium alloys)). Thus, the outcome of the work with improved feedback strategies can be monitored and the progress documented after each feedback action is implemented.

The second part of the evaluation is an assessment of how the implementation of feedback from the re-use process companies proceeded, i.e. whether the implementation occurred as planned and what unforeseen factors may have influenced the outcome. In this stage it is also relevant to re-evaluate the implementation plan. Since companies operate in a changing environment, it is possible that the vision and/or the implementation plan must be revised. Alterations of the market, financial situation, technology developments or intra-organisational restructures, etc., may impact the plan. Hence, this part of the evaluation step adds a dynamic aspect to the framework. The main reason for this dynamic dimension is that the framework need not be discarded even though external or internal factors may interfere with the initial implementation plans. As the evaluation is complete, the implementation will continue with the next action until the results are aligned with the desired vision. Continuous improvement should then be applied throughout the steps of the DfRP framework.

3 Implementing the Collaborative Product-Service Design methods in CarE-Service

The collaborative product-service design method described in Chapter 2 will be performed in all three value chains within the *CarE-Service project*. In order to understand and better set the vision in Step 2 of the DfRP framework, the requirements and KPIs developed for the *CarE-Service project* in WP-1 will be studied prior to the start of the re-design process. These requirements and KPIs are described in Deliverable D1.1 to D1.3. In addition, there are several **facilitators** within the *CarE-Service project* that also supports the collaborative product-service design method described in this document e.g.;

Stakeholder group – the stakeholder group (SG) will be contacted to participate during the actors and system mapping in order to achieve a better picture of the value chain than just using the *CarE-Service project* partners. This means that for each of the three value chains specific stakeholders from the stakeholder group will be contacted to join interviews and workshops.

Consumer committee – the consumer committee (CC) will be contacted in order to get their point of view of how the actors and system map looks like. Through open innovation (Chesbrough, 2004) and by support of the ICT Platform developed in *CarE-service project* the consumers direct feedback on product, service and systems will be considered in the development of future E&HEV. In addition, CC participants will also be consulted in order to better understand the requirements on the product service systems including the future E&HEVs.

ICT Platform – the ICT Platform also developed in the *CarE-Service project* will be an excellent facilitator to achieve better and faster information flows both forward and backward in the three value chains. The ICT platform will be an efficient solution to many existing information flow problems that normally exist in the life cycle of product as illustrated in Figure 1. The ICT Platform is being developed in WP-6 in this *CarE-Service project*.

According to Koenig and Filek (2018) co-design/co-creation methodologies such as “design thinking”, or in this case DfRP framework, are a possibility to start influencing and changing mindsets, raise awareness, and move faster in the direction of a circular economy approach, as the stakeholder group will be involved in the process and be made responsible for the

outcomes. Still, their will and wish to bring about change and their positive attitude are required, as is, from the companies' side, a willingness to invest. If...

- a designer as creator,
- a company as producer, and
- a client as user

...act in a visionary way and feel responsible for our future, health, environment, etc., they might already be very much aware of using re-used and remanufactured products and components, recycled materials resulting from a circular economy approach. The collaborative product-service design methodology proposed is one of truly involving the stakeholder group – in order to gain insight in all their desires and needs.

Still, it is necessary to keep in mind that Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are involved and that they should be considered and protected by all means; the more people and stakeholders are involved, the more important this becomes. Koenig and Filek (2018)

After the development of the design methods all the **CarE-Service project** members will be informed about the methodology to follow in the upcoming steps. A large workshop will be held with all partners where the Actors and Systems mapping will be performed. This is then base for the DfRP framework by also using the input from deliverables from the other work packages of this **CarE-Service project** e.g. WP-1 and WP-6.

4 Conclusions

Within this document a collaborative product-service design method contains the basis from the two major methods of “Actors and System Maps – A Methodology for Developing Product/Service Systems” developed by Desai et al (2017) and “Design-for-Re-use-Processes framework” developed by Lindkvist Haziri and Sundin (2019) is presented. As parts of these two methods are merged and customized together for this **CarE-Service project**, they will be used by the researchers in Task 3.2 to 3.4 where the actual re-design will occur on the E&HEV parts and components within the three value chains.

The collaborative product-service design method and the facilitators described in subchapter 2 and 3 of this document will be used in order to achieve a successful re-design of product and services within the **CarE-Service project**. The design method described within this deliverable will also be useful after the project has ended and also by other companies as this is a public report.

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